
The Role of Artificial Intelligence in changing Leadership Development Programs – Systematic Review

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15534251

Abstract:

The need for leaders has increased multifold, thus creating a scope for internal and external candidates to fulfill the position. Programs like Leadership development helps organization to upskill and reskill employees considered as high potential to take up new roles. To ensure that these roles stay current, it is extremely important that we incorporate technology that will enable leaders to take decisions which are unbiased, data centric and culturally right. One of the tools to do the same is artificial intelligence (AI). The systematic review aims to understand the changes leadership programs have gone through due to artificial intelligence (AI). The review also explores how artificial intelligence (AI) can help leaders to navigate the VUCA world, with ever changing demand. Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a significant role in transforming the way teams are managed. The leadership is now expected to take decisions based on the data, keep communication open, be innovative and ensure that new pathways are embraced, while keeping human culture and empathy intact.

Keywords: Leadership Development Program, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Organizational Impact, Training

Introduction:

Traditional leadership development programs (LDPs) have focused on functional and behavioural skills. With increasing influence of artificial intelligence, the demand for leadership has surged to unprecedented levels. It is imperative that new leaders are equipped with required skills, insights and mindset to successfully navigate seismic shift in organizational landscape. With increasing demand of leaders companies are now investing heavily in learning and development of skills that will create future ready leaders.

New training programs must address the critical need of data driven decisions, unbiased view, and augmented human capabilities. Thus, empowering leaders in systematically analysing trends, manpower planning, optimal utilization of resources,

and implementing strategies with higher accuracy.

Objectives:

1. To review the changing plot of leadership development program (LDP) due artificial intelligence (AI)
2. To explore avenues where artificial intelligence (AI) can assist leaders.
3. To determine changing needs of leadership development programs.

Review of Literature:

Leadership is defined in many ways in various literatures, Stephen Covey (2023) defines it as, “Through years of study, teaching and working with people all over the world, from all walks of life, I have determined that leadership is communicating to people their worth and potential in a way

that is so clear that they come to see it in themselves.”

Napoleon Bonaparte (2019), “A leader is a dealer in hope.”

Erickson and Harvey (2011), “Leaders are not always interested in effecting change for the purpose of benefiting the organization and its members as a whole: rather, the leader may be more interested in personal outcomes”

Artificial intelligence (AI) driven Leadership development programs:

Leomar M. Pago (2024) highlights the AI is an architect of enhanced decision-making. It clearly indicates that the underlying trends and patterns identified with available data helps leaders take more informed decisions and actionable strategies. It also refers to clear communication mode with the team members to seek collaboration. According to John McCarthy(1955), ”the science and engineering of making intelligent machines is artificial intelligence,” The development and functioning of supercomputers indicates how far we have progressed. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as the ability of a machine to carry out operations such as reasoning and problem-solving like human (McKinsey & Company). AI has indeed revolutionized the HR. As articulated by Ramesh Nyathani (2023), human resource analytics have become more strategically advanced and driven by data rather than content alone. As he goes on to elaborate, the ability or skills AI possesses to recognize patterns, find correlations, and make predictions assists HR experts to take action, which is almost impossible to do using the classical methods of analytics.

Martin Saposato (2024) emphasized that behavioral theories have a vast impact on leadership styles. The focus on behaviors, actions, interaction provides a lot of clues to the predictive behaviors. Integrated AI can help analyze these behaviors by looking at multiple data sources and help leaders to

project the expected outcomes.

Mitra Madanchian et. Al (2024) mention that by utilizing AI leadership promotes more adaptable, data-driven, and customized approaches leading to long term organizational benefit. By utilizing AI, leaders can enhance communication and collaboration, anticipate talent needs and real-time analysis which will help in removing biases. Not jus that, it can customize the leadership programs.

Methodology:

The systematic review focuses on the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in reshaping leadership development programs. A qualitative approach has been applied to the review, by analyzing various literature available on internet in the form of research papers, books, articles and podcast. The search was completed by using keywords, AI related programs and interviews, and studying leadership development programs. Studied literature has been systematically segregated and coded. The findings have been concluded by critically evaluating the literature and identifying further scope of research.

Findings:

Artificial intelligence has the capability to customise individual learning and growth roadmap. It can help in customising the program as per individual capacity and learning pattern. This tailored program can create a great leadership development experience, without taking away the human intervention requirement of coaching, mentoring and human conversations.

Leadership development programs have undergone a fundamental change and are now incorporating newer technologies to cope with challenges faced by the new age leaders. Upskilling and reskilling knowledge about AI helps in resolving the challenge of accurate data driven decision making.

The leaders will also have to address the anxiety around artificial intelligence (AI). This is possible within open communication and addressing concern. Leaders will have to embrace the change and help employees overcome the insecurities related to replacement of role by technology.

Leadership development programs ultimate aim it's to create talent pipeline. With the help of artificial intelligence corporates can now discover high potential individual through effective evaluations and analysing trends by keeping a track of current performance so

Issues under consideration:

1. Skill vs. Will of HR fraternity to accept AI
2. Ethical considerations
3. Human Centered Leadership approach
4. Insecurity of people about AI technology

Conclusion:

Leadership development programs must be an encompassment of technology and behavioral sciences. HR should take full advantage of generative AI to personalize the program. The program should enable the leadership members to take more informed decisions while ensuring that the empathetic side is not compromised. The programs should propagate an open communication and query handling regarding the newer ways of operational methodologies. This will not only address the anxiety around AI but also help in creating stronger trust in the leadership. Though with AI the countless possibilities are open, the concern around ethics and culture will continue to persist and will need further study.

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